

Surgical Outcomes in Hepatic Hydatid Disease: A Case Series of 153 Patients

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Abstract

Hepatic hydatid disease, caused by *Echinococcus granulosus*, remains a significant public health concern in endemic regions. This retrospective study analyzed 153 cases treated surgically at the General Surgery Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital in Casablanca from 2019 to 2022. The majority of patients were women from rural areas, with a mean age of 45. Right upper quadrant pain was the predominant symptom. Diagnosis was primarily based on ultrasound using the Gharbi classification, with CT and MRI providing further anatomical detail. The most affected hepatic segments were VI, VII, and VIII. All patients underwent open surgery, mainly via right subcostal laparotomy, with dome resection being the most common technique. Biliary fistulas were identified in 13.72% of cases. Postoperative recovery was uneventful in over 93% of patients, with a low recurrence rate. The discussion highlights the importance of imaging in diagnosis, the role of serology, and surgical principles, including intraoperative exploration and bile duct assessment. Although drug therapy and minimally invasive methods are evolving, open surgery remains the cornerstone of treatment in complex or advanced cases.

Introduction

Hepatic hydatid disease, also known as cystic echinococcosis, is a parasitic infection caused by the larval stage of the tapeworm *Echinococcus granulosus*. This zoonotic disease primarily affects the liver, accounting for approximately 50% to 70% of cases, though it can also involve other organs such as the lungs, spleen, kidneys, and brain [1].

The life cycle of *E. granulosus* involves canines as definitive hosts and ungulates, such as sheep, as intermediate hosts. Humans become accidental intermediate hosts through the ingestion of parasite eggs, often via contaminated food, water, or direct contact with infected animals [2].

The clinical presentation of hepatic hydatid disease varies widely. Many individuals remain asymptomatic for years, with cysts often discovered incidentally during imaging studies for unrelated conditions. When symptoms do occur, they may include abdominal pain, hepatomegaly, and, in cases of biliary involvement, jaundice. Complications can arise from cyst rupture, leading to anaphylaxis or secondary infections, and from compression of adjacent structures.

Advancements in imaging techniques have significantly enhanced the diagnosis of hepatic hydatid cysts. Ultrasonography is commonly used as the initial diagnostic tool due to its accessibility and effectiveness in detecting cystic lesions. Computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provide detailed information regarding the size, location, and characteristics of the cysts, as well as their relationship with adjacent structures, aiding in preoperative planning [3].

The management of hepatic hydatid disease is multifaceted, involving medical therapy, surgical intervention, and percutaneous techniques. The choice of treatment depends on factors such as cyst size, location, stage, and the presence of complications. Surgical removal of the cyst remains a primary treatment modality, especially for large or complicated cysts.

Minimally invasive procedures, such as percutaneous aspiration, injection, and reaspiration (PAIR), have also been employed in selected cases.

Adjunctive antiparasitic therapy with agents like albendazole is often used to reduce the risk of recurrence.

More Information

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Despite being a well-recognized condition, hepatic hydatid disease continues to pose significant public health challenges, particularly in endemic regions. A comprehensive understanding of its epidemiology, clinical manifestations, diagnostic modalities, and treatment options is essential for effective management and control of this disease.

Presentation of Cases

This is a retrospective study involving 135 patients who underwent surgery for hepatic hydatid cysts in the General Surgery Department (AILE1) of Ibn Rochd University Hospital in Casablanca, over a four-year period from January 1, 2019, to December 30, 2022.

Between January 1, 2019, and the end of December 2022, a total of 153 cases of hepatic hydatid cysts (HHC) were recorded out of 2,423 hospitalizations (6.32%) in the General Surgery Department (AILE1) at the Ibn Rochd University Hospital Center in Casablanca.

The average age of the patients was 45 years, with the most affected age group being 40 to 49 years, representing 43 cases (28.10%). There was a female predominance, with 93 women (60.78%) and a sex ratio of 0.64.

In terms of geographic distribution, the majority of patients (66.67%) were from rural areas, while 33.33% were from urban settings—most of whom reported having spent their childhood in rural environments. A history of contact with dogs was noted in 106 patients (69.28%), and 56 patients (36.6%) had a previous history of surgically treated HHC.

Pain was the most frequent presenting symptom, reported in 142 patients (92.81%). It was localized to the right hypochondrium in 134 cases (87.58%) and described as a heaviness-type discomfort in 134 cases (94.36%). Eight patients (5.23%) presented with or had a recent history of cholestatic jaundice. In 11 patients (7.18%), the hepatic hydatid cyst was asymptomatic and incidentally discovered during abdominal ultrasonography.

Abdominal ultrasound was performed in all patients and allowed confirmation of the diagnosis of hepatic hydatid cysts according to the Gharbi classification. Single cysts were observed in 86 patients (56.21%). The right lobe of the liver was involved in 117 cases (76.47%), with segments VI, VII, and VIII being the most frequently affected. There were 21 univesicular cysts (stage 1) accounting for 24.71%, 28 multiseptated cysts with thin septa (stage 3) representing 32.94% (figure 1), and 19 echogenic cysts with tissue-like structure (stage 4).

Abdominal CT scans were systematically performed preoperatively for all patients. CT imaging revealed biliary duct dilation in 10 patients (6.53%), with visualization of hydatid material within the bile ducts in 3 cases. Peritoneal hydatidosis was identified in 7

patients, abscessed hepatic hydatid cysts in 3 patients, and splenic involvement in 2 cases.

Figure 1: Ultrasound Image Showing a Multivesicular Cystic Formation Classified as Type 3

MRI was performed in 30 patients (19.6%). It revealed biliary duct dilation in 2 patients (figure 2), fistulization into the bile ducts with the presence of hydatid material in 3 patients, and peritoneal hydatidosis in 2 cases.

Chest radiography was performed in all patients to screen for associated pulmonary hydatid cysts. It showed elevation of the right diaphragmatic dome in 23 cases (15.03%). This finding was further investigated with a thoracic CT scan, which revealed in one patient a ruptured left posterobasal pulmonary hydatid cyst, opening into a subsegmental bronchus and in contact with the pleura and diaphragm.

Figure 2: An MRI Image Suggestive of Large Hydatid Cysts with Membrane Detachment and Dilation of the Intrahepatic Bile Ducts

Serology was requested for 152 patients, and it was positive in 128 patients (83.66%). The techniques used in our series were indirect hemagglutination and ELISA. Among the 153 treated cases, the treatment was surgical and performed through an open approach. The surgical approach was right subcostal in 133 patients and median supraumbilical in 16 patients. Biliary fistula was identified in 21 patients (13.72%) and was treated by blind ligation of the fistula in 20 cases (95.23%) and a transhepatic cystic duct choledochotomy according to Per Dromo in one case.

The resection of the prominent dome according to the Lagrot technique was our preferred therapeutic method, performed in 151 cases (98.69%). A pericystectomy of an exophytic cyst associated with resection of the prominent dome was performed in a single patient, and a hepatotomy with evacuation of a hydatid cyst was carried out in one patient with the help of intraoperative hepatic ultrasound.

Figure 3: Intraoperative Image of a Large Cysto-Biliary Fistula in a Patient from Our Study Series

Figure 4: Intraoperative Image Showing Transperitoneal-Hepatic Drainage of the Cysto-Biliary Fistula and Drainage of the Common Bile Duct via a Kehr Drain (Perdromo Procedure)

Retrograde cholecystectomy was performed in 24 patients, including 2 for cysto-vesicular fistula and 21 for gallbladder stones. Drainage of the dilated main bile duct was done with a Kehr drain in 2 patients, and resection of peritoneal hydatid cysts was performed in 7 patients.

In our series, helminthic treatment with albendazole was prescribed for a single patient who had a history of liver hydatid cyst and had undergone surgery four times.

The postoperative course was uncomplicated in 143 cases (93.46%). The average postoperative length of stay in our series was 6 days; however, two cases of recurrence were observed during the study period.

Discussion

The frequency of hepatic hydatid cysts

Hydatidosis is an anthroponozoonosis caused by the development of the larva of the dog tapeworm *Echinococcus Granulosis* in humans. It primarily affects individuals with low socio-economic status, living in conditions of inadequate hygiene, as well as people in contact with stray dogs, particularly shepherds³. It is considered endemic in certain regions, notably in Peru, Chile, Argentina, Uruguay, southern Brazil, the Mediterranean region, Central Asia, western China, and East Africa. The incidence in humans can exceed 50 cases per 100,000 person-years in endemic areas, and prevalence rates as high as 5% to 10% can be observed in certain parts of Peru, Argentina, East Africa, and China [4].

Age distribution

Hepatic hydatidosis can occur at any age, particularly in adulthood. This is primarily due to the slow progression of the cyst.

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>/ Average Age</i>
Mesut A. & al	2001	40
Roland C. & al	2003	40,4
Moudjahid M & Tahdine T	2011	35
Belamalem. S & Auj	2014	36,8
Li Ma & De-Cai Chen	2020	39,9
Our series	2023	45

Figure 5: Distribution of KHF Cases by Age in Different Series

Source: [5-7]

Often, the infestation occurs during childhood, but the cyst does not manifest or is not diagnosed until adulthood. This slow progression is attributed to the dense nature of the hepatic parenchyma compared to the more flexible pulmonary parenchyma, where cyst growth is faster and complications occur earlier. Our study reveals that the age group of 40-49 years is the

most affected, with an average age of 45 years. For comparison, the table below reports the age distribution as reported by some authors.

Contact with Dogs

Contact with dogs is the main risk factor for hydatid disease. It is found in 79% of cases in the study by M. Chegri, M. Oulad S, and 82.7% in the study by F. HLIL [8]. In our series, it is estimated at 69.28%.

Functional Signs

The discovery of a hepatic hydatid cyst can occur in various circumstances. Often, patients present no symptoms until the cyst reaches a certain size or undergoes a complication. In such cases, the discovery may be incidental during medical imaging examinations performed for other reasons.

Abdominal pain remains the most important sign [9]. This pain often localizes in the right hypochondrium, sometimes in the epigastric region, and is described as a feeling of heaviness or stretching, progressively worsening. In our series, pain in the right hypochondrium is the primary symptom, present in 87.58% of cases.

Jaundice is a sign that suggests bile duct compression or rupture. In adults, it constitutes a major clinical symptom [10].

Paraclinical Diagnosis

Abdominal Ultrasound

Ultrasound is the imaging modality of choice due to its availability, lack of radiation, and ability to provide high resolution for the diagnosis, staging, differential diagnosis, and follow-up of most abdominal cystic lesions. Additionally, it is commonly used in the interventional treatment of echinococcosis [11]. Doppler ultrasound allows for the evaluation of the relationship between the lesion and adjacent vascular structures (portal veins, hepatic veins, inferior vena cava) and the presence or absence of dilation of intra- or extrahepatic bile ducts [9].

The ultrasound images of the hydatid cyst have been grouped into five categories, based on the work of Gharbi regarding hepatic hydatid cysts [12]:

Gharbi type	WHO type	Cyst morphology
I	CE 1	Unilocular anechoic lesion with double line sign
III	CE 2	Multiseptated rosette like honeycomb cyst
II	CE 3A	Cyst with detached membranes (water-lily sign)
III	CE 3B	Cyst with daughter cysts in solid matrix
IV	CE 4	Cyst with heterogeneous hypoechoic/hyperechoic contents. No daughter cysts
V	CE 5	Solid plus calcified wall

Figure 6: Gharbi and WHO Hydatid Cysts Classifications

In our series, we used Gharbi's classification, where type 3 is the most frequent, representing 32.94% of cases. These results align with those reported by Chourak [13] (26.4%) and Blairon [14] (32.14%). This consistency can be explained by the short interval between infestation and the discovery of the cyst, which accounts for the predominance of young and uncomplicated forms.

The preferential involvement of the right hemiliver is classic in the literature. An anatomical hypothesis could explain this asymmetry: the right hepatic parenchyma represents more than 60% of the total hepatic parenchyma and is irrigated by a larger portal branch, the direction of which is in continuity with the portal trunk. In contrast, the left portal vein branch diverges from the portal trunk at nearly a right angle [15]. In our series, the right liver (76.47%) is more affected than the left liver (14.38%). F. Klotz reports the same observation [9] (58%), as do Sakhri [16] (65%) and Blairon [14] (57.1%).

Abdominal Tomography (CT scan)

CT is a complementary exam that is not routinely used for the diagnosis of hydatid cysts of the liver but is employed in various situations as it provides superior performance compared to ultrasound in localizing the hydatid cyst, determining its size, and assessing its relationships with vascular and biliary structures, as well as adjacent organs. It is particularly useful when the diagnosis is complex, especially for types I, IV, and V of Gharbi's classification, which correspond to CE1, CE4, and CE5 types in the WHO classification [17,18]. It helps eliminate differential diagnoses, such as biliary cysts, hepatic angiomas, adenomas, hepatocellular carcinomas, liver abscesses, or hepatic metastases in their cystic form. CT is also recommended in cases of multiple hydatid cyst localization, complicated hydatid cysts, or hydatid recurrence. Moreover, the scan can detect small-sized cysts.

On CT, hydatid cysts appear hypodense compared to normal liver tissue, with well-defined contours and surrounded by a thick wall visible both before and after the injection of contrast material [18].

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

On MRI, the wall of the hydatid cyst appears hypointense on both T1- and T2-weighted sequences. The different types of hydatid cysts, such as the detachment of the proliferating membrane or the presence of daughter vesicles, can be clearly identified. MRI can prove to be more relevant than CT for detecting complications, such as communication with the bile ducts or superinfection of the cystic cavity [19].

Figure 7: 3D Reconstruction of a Biliary MRI Showing Dilatation of the Intrahepatic Bile Ducts Containing Endoluminal Material (Yellow Arrow)

Chest X-ray

Previously, chest X-rays were prescribed to screen for potential pulmonary localization of a hydatid cyst, to evaluate the presence of a reactive pleuritis linked to a hepatic hydatid cyst, and to assess the state of the pulmonary parenchyma in preoperative evaluations. However, chest X-rays can also detect calcified hepatic hydatid cysts [20].

Hydatid Serology

Serology remains a key element in the diagnosis and follow-up of hydatidosis, guiding the diagnosis in 80 to 95% of cases [21]. It is based on the detection of specific antibodies using quantitative techniques (indirect immunofluorescence, hemagglutination, ELISA) and qualitative techniques (immunoelectrophoresis, co-electrophoresis, immuno-imprints, or Western blot) [22]. After surgical removal, serology may become positive or increase, then gradually decrease, eventually becoming negative within two years. However, in cases of persistence, recurrence, or secondary localization, a thorough clinical and radiological evaluation is required [3].

Treatment

The treatment of hydatid disease remains primarily surgical, despite the contribution of drug therapy.

To date, the main strategies for surgical treatment of cystic echinococcosis (CE) include classical and laparoscopic techniques of enucleation and excision, as well as percutaneous puncture-drainage interventions (PAIR) [23].

The goal of surgical treatment is [24]:

- Direct inactivation of the parasite.
- Evacuation of the cyst with elimination of the germinal layer and the pericystic area.
- Prevention of peritoneal dissemination of the scolices.
- Treatment of the radicular duct, thus resolving complications and the possibility of recurrence.

Surgical Treatment Steps:

1. Sterilization and removal of the parasite.
2. Removal of the residual cavity.

3. Identification of bile duct fistulas and control of the main bile duct.

Access Routes

Right Subcostal Laparotomy

This is the most commonly used approach. It provides excellent exposure of all hepatic segments when the incision is extended adequately on the right or left border [9]. In our study, it was used in 133 patients (86.93%), in 81.34% of cases in HLILI's series [8], 52.5% in Daali et al.'s series [25], and 96.9% in Blairon's series [14].

Midline Supraumbilical Laparotomy

It facilitates access to left hepatic hydatid cysts and other abdominal localizations, but the involvement of the right liver, particularly the hepatic dome and vascular pedicle, poses challenges [26]. In our series, this approach was used in 16 cases (10.46%), 17.33% in HLILI's series [8], 16.7% in Daali et al.'s series [25], and 3.1% in Blairon's series [14].

Bilateral Subcostal Incision

This approach allows easy release of diaphragmatic adhesions and good vascular and biliary control.

Laparoscopic Treatment

Laparoscopic treatment of hepatic hydatid cysts offers several advantages, particularly in terms of postoperative comfort and reducing hospital stay duration. Case series have shown the efficacy of this approach for accessible (anterior and superficial) and uncomplicated cysts of type I or II, with associated antiparasitic treatment pre- and postoperatively. However, disadvantages have also been reported, primarily related to the risk of hydatid fluid leakage during aspiration, which could lead to peritoneal contamination. Moreover, laparoscopic accessibility to posterior-superior cysts can be difficult. To mitigate leakage risks, techniques such as the use of an umbrella trocar, suction grinders, or the Palanivelu Hydatid System (PHS) have been employed. While studies have indicated that laparoscopic access to hepatic hydatid cysts is feasible, no comparative or randomized studies have yet recommended this approach as a systematic first choice [27].

Intraoperative Exploration

This procedure should be systematically performed after thorough cleaning of the endocyst. It allows precise localization, characterization, and relationships of the hepatic hydatid cyst. It also helps identify potential peritoneal grafts [28]. The results of this exploration guide the adaptation of the surgical procedure.

Intraoperative Ultrasound

Intraoperative ultrasound, as in any hepatic surgery, is of great importance. Its utility is both diagnostic and therapeutic. It allows for better precision in identifying the relationships between the cyst and vascular pedicles, especially for central cysts. This examination

is crucial in guiding the operative strategy. It is also relevant for multiple hepatic hydatid cysts, helping count and localize the cysts while ensuring the absence of residual cysts [28].

Cholangiography

Cholangiography is particularly useful in reorienting the therapeutic strategy when a major biliary communication is discovered incidentally during the procedure. It is generally performed after cyst evacuation and is recommended when there are signs suggesting the migration of daughter vesicles into the main bile duct (jaundice, biological cholestasis, dilation of bile ducts on ultrasound, or identification of a large cysto-biliary fistula during surgery). Its use is recommended for large cysts, central cysts, incomplete exploration of the residual cavity, and multiple cysts [29].

Protection of the Abdominal Cavity

Protection against contamination of the abdominal cavity is ensured by surrounding the operative field around the cyst with sterile drapes or sponges impregnated with scolicidal solutions. Two aspirators with transparent tubing (to evaluate the aspirated fluid) should be prepared, one for aspirating the cyst contents and the other on standby to quickly aspirate any hydatid fluid leaks [27].

Evacuation and Destruction of the Parasite

The dome of the cyst is perforated using a large trocar and evacuated by vigorous aspiration to reduce the internal cyst pressure and prevent a vacuum shock. Then, the opening of the pericyst allows for the elimination of hydatid debris and the proliferative membrane. The hydatid fluid should be checked for its appearance: clear (like spring water), purulent, or bile-like [27]. The pericyst is cleaned using a sponge impregnated with scolicidal agents.

Scolicidal Agents

Hypertonic Saline Solution

Hypertonic saline is only parasitocidal at a concentration of 20%. Its use in large volumes, especially on the operative field, can lead to hydro-electrolytic disturbances such as hypernatremia [30]. It is recommended to use a 20% saline solution and avoid injecting it under pressure into the cyst to prevent its passage into the bile ducts.

Hydrogen Peroxide (2% or 3%)

Hydrogen peroxide's parasitocidal effect is very effective in vitro, but its use is hindered by the significant foam formation in the operative field and the risk of hyperpressure following its injection into the cyst. Exceptional cases of gas embolism have been reported after hydrogen peroxide use [28]. In our series, hydrogen peroxide was used in all patients.

Conservative Methods

The most commonly used therapeutic method is the conservative surgical approach. This involves

inactivating the cyst, evacuating its contents, and treating the residual cavity [31]. This technique preserves the pericyst, avoiding the risks of dissection of the adjacent parenchyma, particularly vascular or biliary injuries. However, it leaves a rigid shell and a residual cavity prone to postoperative collections [16].

Recession of the Protruding Dome

The Recession of the Protruding Dome, or Lagrot procedure, involves excising the protruding part of the pericyst. This is done using scissors or an electric scalpel directly above the pericyst (figure 8). It does not involve manipulation of healthy hepatic parenchyma. Hemostasis and biliostasis are ensured by sutures or separate stitches. Finally, external drainage of the residual cavity is performed using a Redon drain connected to a sterile container. For small, lower-growing cysts with no bile duct communication, the RDS technique may create a flat, inclined cavity, and abdominal drainage may not be necessary [28]. In our series, this technique was used in 98.25% of cases.

Figure 8: Lagrot Technique:
A. The protruding part of the pericyst is progressively sectioned with an electric scalpel a few millimeters from the hepatic junction.
B. Hemostatic suturing is performed on the edges of the resection. The residual cavity is drained with a Redon drain.

The residual cavity is preferably drained using a double-lumen Salem tube or a Kehr drain, positioned at the bottom of the residual cavity to prevent fluid retention

that could lead to infections. This device is used for irrigation and postoperative lavage [6]. In our series, we used Redon drains and Salem tubes for drainage. The management of the residual cavity involves its drainage and filling to prevent complications.

Treatment of the Residual Cavity

Figure 9: The Residual Cavity is Filled with the Omentum and Drained with an Aspirative Redon Drain

The treatment of the residual cavity involves drainage and filling. This helps avoid complications and includes:

- Epiploplasty: A technique that involves filling the residual cavity with the greater omentum,

Figure 10: Pericystectomy Plan:

A. The pericystectomy plane corresponds to the dashed line. The Glisson's capsule is incised with an electric scalpel at the contact point with the pericyst.

B. The fenestrated forceps hold the edge of the pericyst, stretching it to expose the progressively distending vascular-biliary structures, which will be ligated or coagulated.

2. Planned Hepatectomy:

Hepatic resections, also known as planned hepatectomies, involve the removal of the hydatid cyst of the liver (HCL) along with the liver tissue in which it is located. This technique is limited and indicated in cases of very large hydatid cysts that are centrally located and close to the major pedicles, or cysts that occupy the entire segment of the liver. It is a relatively complex procedure, requiring an experienced surgeon,

exploiting its physiological properties of secretion, absorption, and phagocytosis (figure 9).

- Capitonnage: Closing the residual cavity by suturing the edges of the cyst wall after treating the pericyst.
- Guedj's Tunnelization: Reducing the residual cavity by a "spiral" suture, centered on an aspirative drain.

Radical Methods

These involve the complete resection of the cyst along with the pericyst [32].

1. Pericystectomy:

Pericystectomy involves the complete removal of the pericyst, which should be fibrous, thick, and of small size (figure 10). The pericyst is separated from the healthy hepatic parenchyma while ensuring biliostasis and hemostasis. There are three variations [33]:

- Total pericystectomy: The entire pericyst is sectioned from the hepatic parenchyma.
- Subtotal pericystectomy: Part of the pericyst is left in contact with a major vascular or biliary structure.
- Pericystoresection: A total pericystectomy is performed along with a hepatic resection, leading to the removal of a small portion of poorly vascularized hepatic parenchyma.

This is the treatment of choice in terms of the risk of recurrence and secondary biliary fistula. The main risk is hemorrhagic [9]. In our series, this technique was used in only one patient, representing 0.65%.

and involves sacrificing more or less significant amounts of healthy hepatic parenchyma [28].

Treatment of Biliocystic Fistula:

1. Cystobiliary Disconnection by Suturing the Fistula:

This procedure involves suturing the fistula using a slow-resorption suture, complemented by a filling technique using omentoplasty. The residual cavity is drained with an aspirative Redon drain. This procedure assumes that the fistula is terminal and is sutured in

soft tissue after localized pericystectomy around the fistula. It can also be combined with the de-obstruction of the main bile ducts (MBD) by draining them with a Kehr drain (figure 11).

Figure 11: Cystobiliary Disconnection by Suturing a Terminal Fistula after Perifistular Perikystectomy.

This technique is indicated for small fistulas, less than 5 mm. However, its major disadvantage lies in the lack of sealing, exposing the patient to the risk of prolonged biliary leakage and the formation of subphrenic abscesses, which can lead to prolonged hospitalizations [34]. In our series, this technique was used in 20 patients (95.23%).

2. Cystobiliary Disconnection by Perdomo's Transhepatic-Cystic Choledocostomy:

Cystobiliary disconnection by transhepatic-cystic choledocostomy aims to separate the main bile duct from the cystic cavity. This procedure involves accessing the main bile duct, placing a multi-perforated T-drain blocked at the upper bile duct convergence. The long branch of the drain is exteriorized through the skin, with an intra-cavitary length of 1 to 2 cm and a transhepatic, parenchymal path of at least 3 cm.

Although this method requires a relatively prolonged hospital stay, it is chosen when other methods are not possible [13] (figure 12). In our series, Perdomo's transhepatic-cystic choledocostomy was performed in one case.

Figure 12: Transperitoneal Hepatocystic Choledocostomy According to Perdomo

3. Trans-fistulo-oddian Internal Drainage:

This approach aims to establish a "natural" drainage of the residual cavity using a preserved large cystobiliary fistula that communicates with the bile ducts. After a thorough cleaning of the residual cavity under visual control, it is securely closed using slowly absorbable sutures attached to the exteriorized perikyst. No intervention is performed at the papilla, and no external drainage is applied to the closed residual cavity. The cavity, which is soft and cleaned, drains through the cystobiliary fistula into the main bile duct and duodenum. A cholecystectomy is performed in association. Generally, the residual cavity spontaneously retracts after 2 to 3 weeks, forming a fibrous scar [28] (figure 13).

Figure 13: Trans-fistulo-oddian Internal Drainage:

A. Trans-fistulo-oddian Internal Drainage

B, C. The residual cavity, once cleaned, is sealed tightly. If the common bile duct has been approached to relieve the bile duct obstruction, it is closed over a Kehr drain.

Medical Treatment

Albendazole has been shown to be more effective than placebo and mebendazole according to randomized

prospective studies, making it the drug of choice [35]. Its dosage is 10 mg/kg/day in two oral doses, in 30-day cycles separated by 15-day intervals [22]. As for side

effects, they mainly involve gastrointestinal symptoms such as epigastric pain, diarrhea, nausea, vomiting, as well as headaches and allergic reactions. Less commonly, liver metabolism disorders, alopecia, and leukopenia have been reported. Albendazole is contraindicated in cases of hepatic cell failure and during pregnancy due to its teratogenicity and embryotoxicity [36].

Indications for Medical Treatment [25]

- Pre-operative: Administering Albendazole before surgery helps sterilize the contents of the cyst, thereby minimizing the risks of dissemination during the procedure.
- Post-operative: Prescribing Albendazole helps prevent possible intra-peritoneal dissemination.
- In non-surgical cases: Albendazole can be prescribed under several circumstances: surgical contraindications, multiple inaccessible localizations, multiple recurrences, or refusal of surgery.

Percutaneous Treatment (PAIR)

PAIR (puncture-aspiration-injection-reaspiration) is a minimally invasive method that involves a percutaneous puncture under ultrasound or CT scan control, followed by aspiration of the cystic fluid using a needle or catheter. Subsequently, the protoscolices remaining in the residual cavity are destroyed by injecting a scolicidal agent, which is then reaspirated. Albendazole is prescribed before and after the procedure. PAIR is indicated for hydatid cysts of types 1 and 2 without biliary fistula [24].

Post-Operative Monitoring

This monitoring mainly relies on chest radiography and abdominal ultrasound at 3-month, 6-month, and 1-year intervals, primarily to assess the nature and condition of the residual cavity. Serological monitoring is recommended when possible, with tests performed at 6 months and 1-year post-surgery. CT scans are reserved for suspected recurrences and for monitoring large residual cavities. Some authors recommend semiannual monitoring for the first two years in endemic areas, followed by annual surveillance until 5 years [28].

Conclusion

Despite efforts over the past three decades to combat Echinococcosis, it remains a major public health issue in Morocco. The frequency of this disease in our country can be attributed to frequent contact between dogs and humans, the importance of pastoral farming, and the lack of developed prophylactic measures. Although considered benign, hydatid disease can lead to complications, especially biliary-cystic fistulas, which can transform it into a severe condition. The clinical presentation of the disease is varied, mainly characterized by abdominal pain and fever syndrome. Advances in medical imaging now enable early and accurate diagnosis, as well as high-quality pre-

therapeutic evaluation, ensuring optimal therapeutic management and contributing to post-therapeutic monitoring.

The treatment of hydatidosis primarily relies on a surgical approach aimed at solving three major issues: elimination of the parasite, management of the residual cavity, and treatment of possible complications. Radical surgical interventions are gaining ground, gradually replacing conservative surgical techniques, with proven advantages in terms of postoperative morbidity.

Long-term surveillance of these patients is crucial due to the frequency of recurrences, especially in difficult-to-reach locations. This monitoring relies on clinical examination, with particular emphasis on radiological and immunological criteria.

Provenance and Peer Review

Not commissioned, externally peer reviewed.

Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical Approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflicts Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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